

Monosemy in phraseological units in the Uzbek and English languages

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Abstract: In the study of monosemy in phraseological units, it has been determined that there are not enough sources about monosemy and polysemy in phraseologisms. Despite those it is tried to be analyzed the linguistic theories consisting of lexical and contextual meaning of monosemantic and polysemantic phraseological units with the help of examples. Moreover, a comprehensive study of these phenomenon can give a broader atmosphere and good chance for in- depth analysis of various features of different systematic languages.

Key words: Phraseological integrity, semantic unity, polysemic word, multiword lexical, fixed expressions, semantic stability, analogy, connotations.

In linguistics, phraseology is the study of set or fixed expressions, such as idioms, phrasal verbs, and other type multi-word lexical units, in which the component parts of the expression take on a meaning more specific than otherwise not predictable from the sum of their meanings when used independently. According to German linguist Rosemarie Glazer a phraseological unit is lexicalized, reproducible polysemic word group in common use, which has relative syntactic and semantic stability, can be idiomized, it can carry connotations and have an emphatic or intensifying function in a text. Vinogradov affords the classification of phraseological units according to the grades of semantic unity in his researches. He characterizes the main features of semantics of phraseological binding and phraseological unity and makes analogy between the phraseological unities and the words in their motivate meaning. He stressed that the meaning of phraseological binding is conditionally and voluntary as the meaning of non-motivated word. It is independent of lexical structure and meaning of elements. In his research work "About types of the phraseological units" he notes the phraseological binding is the semantic unit which is homogeneous to the word without inner form. The researchers limits phraseological unities to phraseological binding.

The perception of motivate meaning of phraseological unity is based upon realization of lexical structure and relation between the whole meaning of expression and meaning of the components of the expression.

- 1) phraseological integrity (Frazelogik butunlik);
- 2) phraseological confusion (Frazelogik chatishma);

1) Phraseological integrity is a phraseological unit that is interpreted on the basis of the meanings of the words in its meaning and expresses a generalized metaphor: belni bog‘lamoq, yog‘ tushsa yalagudek;

2) Phraseological confusion is a phraseological unit whose meaning is not connected with the lexical meanings of the words it contains, and on the basis of which it cannot be explained: xamir uchidan patir, tarvuzi qo‘ltig‘idan tushdi; The development of lexical meaning is also characteristic of phraseological units. In modern Uzbek and English phraseological units, lexical meaning has developed mainly as a result of metaphorical transference. For example, the phraseological unit “yoqmay qolmoq” due to the frequent consumption of a food. This phraseological unit was later used to refer to things other than food, as well as to people, and as a result of such a transference, this phraseological unit became inconsistent with it, meaning “yoqtirmaslik hissi uyg‘ondi”. And there is a similar meaning in the phraseological unit “to walk all over somebody” in English. Mastava ko‘ngillaringizga tegib yurgandir. Ammo har kuni bir xil narsani takrorlayverish uning ko‘ngliga tegdi. I’m not about to let them walk all over me. You need to discipline your students, so that they don’t walk all over you. A phraseological unit also has opposite lexical meanings. For example, the phraseological unit of yuragi qinidan chiqayozdi means intense excitement, but such a situation is associated with both anxiety and joy: 1) Qo‘rqamayman deb bo‘lmaydi ,o‘g‘lim .Shunaqa vaqtda odamning yuragi qinidan chiqib ketadi. 2) Qizning paranjisini ko‘rgani bilanoq yigitning yuragi qinidan chiqayozdi Most phraseological units are monosemantic. For example, the phraseological unit bahridan o‘tmoq means to give up what you know is useful, bergisini aytguncha urib o‘ldirmoq, and in English go over somebody’s head means not understanding anything and another phraseologism get down to brass tacks means to start discussing an important issue”. Most polysemantic phraseological units have two or three meanings in the Uzbek language. For example, the phrase boshi aylandi has two meanings: 1) behuda bo‘lmoq; Stol yoniga kelguncha uning boshi aylanib ketdi. (S.Zunnunova) 2) esankiramoq; Muloyim qarab qo‘yishlaridan uning boshi aylanib ketdi. (Said Ahmad) The phraseological unit be living on borrowed time has two meanings: 1) living in an unexpectedly short time, 2) being close to death. The phraseological unit bosh suqmoq also has three meanings: 1) gavgdasi tashqarida qolib, boshini suqqan holda qaramoq, 2) kirmoq, 3) aralashmoq, halaqit bermoq or to beg the question: 1)to avoid the question, 2) to raise a basic question or to consider it important 3) to consider a debate or a question as having been proved Monosemy is considered to be specific to the period of initial use of a newly created word as well as a newly

acquired word. The terms are also usually monosemantic for instance metallurgical terms: absorber -yutiluvchi; magnetitemagnitit; mining terms: amalgamation-amalgamatsiya; rock debris -shag'al; Monosemantic words include Proper nouns. For example: in English: Cambridge University, Manchester City. In Uzbek: National University of Uzbekistan. Each word is monosemantic in its creation; it appears as an object, a sign, a noun. It then serves as a name for other events, thereby changing its meaning and evolving. As a result, various semantic shifts in the meaning of the word occur, and as a result, the monosemantic word becomes a polysemantic word. Polysemy is specific to both lexical units and grammatical units. Accordingly, polysemy is divided into two types: 1) Lexical polysemy — a phenomenon of ambiguity in lexical units: Boil the solution once with salt and once with sugar. Once Germany had surrendered, the Soviets were free to enter the conflict against Japan. In Uzbek: Bug'doy maydoni, energiya maydoni, futbol maydoni, jang maydoni Darvozabon maydonni tark etdi.(futbol maydoni) 2) Grammatical polysemy — The phenomenon of ambiguity in grammatical units: a) Students need some paper.(paper means in this sentence a sheet of paper for writing something) . b) Everybody should read the paper. (In the second sentence paper means newspaper for reading). Lexical polysemy itself is separated into 2 types: 1. Lexical polysemy is a phenomenon of ambiguity in words. 2. Phraseological polysemy is a phenomenon of ambiguity in expressions: ko' zga ko'rinmoq 1-tanilmoq- to be known, ko'zga ko'rinmoq 2-o'ziga e'tiborni tortmoq- to draw attention. Lexical polysemy is a multiple and complex phenomenon. The development of the lexical meaning of almost every word requires a concrete, individual approach. Therefore, it is very difficult to identify and systematize lexical meanings. General ideas about the polysemy of a word usually only serve to give an idea of the development of the lexical meaning of the word. Polysemantic words are divided into two types according to the ability of lexical meanings to perform other categorical functions or not: 1) simple polysemantic words 2) complex polysemantic words. Apparently, all polysemantic words in the verb and pronoun categories are simple polysemantic words. Complex polysemantic words are found in words related to nouns, adjective, and adverbs. Simple polysemantic words are almost non-existent among the polysemantic words of the category of adjective and adverb. Because the words in these two categories are almost identical, they share their functions. Numerals perform almost the same function in speech as adjectives. Among the words belonging to the category of nouns, both simple polysemantic words and complex polysemantic words are found. Both English and Uzbek languages, polysemy is a widespread phenomenon, approached in two ways:

diachronically and synchronically. Changes in the semantic structure of a word require diachronic study. Diachronically, polysemy refers to the fact that a word retains its original meaning and at the same time acquires one or another new meaning. A diachronic semantic analysis of the English words *sweet* has been revealed that its original meaning pleasant to the taste and the meaning one of four basic sensations, like that of sugar was its derivative, while in Modern English the latter has become central and now is placed first in dictionaries. A synchronical approach to polysemy is the co-occurrence of different meanings of the same word in a given historical period and the determination of these meanings in the semantic structure of the word. It is well known that among linguistic units, language is considered to be changeable over time, its meanings evolve, resulting in new derivative meanings around the main meaning. Almost every word has its own contextual meaning, and in some cases the main meaning loses its meaning as a result of the formation of derivative meaning. While some meanings are characterized by permanence, some meanings change over time; they appear only in certain contexts, and this meaning is not recorded in dictionaries. The main and derivative meanings are relatively unchanged, and therefore they form the semantic structure of the word and are recorded in dictionaries. The problem of ambiguity is one of the most discussed problems in lexicology. Polysemy is one of the separate categories of lexicology. Each polysemantic word has its own stylistic features, and the analysis of the lexical meanings in it requires a lot of research and observation. It is well known that context is important for the meaning of polysemantic words. Because polysemantic words have several lexical meanings, and in the context it has only one meaning. In English, in contrast to Uzbek, the contexts that define the meaning of a polysemantic word are divided into three: Lexical context; Grammatical context; Extralinguistic context; In a lexical context, lexical groups that related to polysemantic words play main role. To do this, let's analyze the polysemantic word *heavy*. The word *heavy* means a great weight. But if it is used with a lexical group denoting natural phenomena, the word has a strong meaning: *heavy wind*, *heavy storm*. Or in *heavy industry*, *heavy artillery* means “heavy” (*heavy industry*, *heavy artillery*). In a grammatical context, the grammatical structure of the text or context helps to determine the meaning of the polysemantic word. For example, the main meaning of the word *make* is to build. But its meaning of urging/forcing only occurs in the / to make + Subject + infinitive Verb /. For example, *to make smb laugh*, *work (to make someone laugh, use)*. Or the meaning of the word only become in the / to make + adjective + noun / grammatical construction. For example, *to make a good wife*, *a devoted teacher*. There is also a

more extralinguistic or situational context in English. Sometimes the meaning of a polysemantic word is not clear in either the lexical context or the grammatical context. In this case, we can only determine the meaning of the polysemantic word from the situation in which it is spoken. For example, the meaning of the word polysemantic in the ring to give smb a ring is determined by the situational context, not the lexical or grammatical context. The word ring polysemantic has the lexical meaning of aylana/halqa and a ring on the phone, to give smb a ring means both to give a ring to someone and to call someone means. The exact meaning of a compound can only be determined by the context in which it is spoken. This is an important function of the extralinguistic or situational context. The process of development of a new meaning (or a change of meaning) is termed transference. Two types of transference are depending on the two types of logical associations underlying the semantic process. Transference based on resemblance (similarity). This type of transference is also referred to as linguistic metaphor. A new meaning appears as a result of associating two objects (phenomena, qualities, etc.) due to their outward similarity. Transference based on contiguity. Another term for this type of transference is linguistic metonymy. Metaphor is based on the affinity or interplay of two meanings of a word – direct and contextual and its usage will be analyzed as follows: Della has beautiful golden hair , here the word combination golden hair means the girls hair is beautiful or the colour of her hair is looks like a golden. And in this sentence, author expresses the meaning by the word “golden” itself. There are other examples like this: It reached below her knees and covered her like a cloak; The next two hours were like a happy dream”. In the third sentence “dream” is described by “happy” and here its meaning changes to contextual meaning rather than the usage of direct one, if we translate it into Uzbek, we can see the differences also: So‘nggi ikki soat xuddi shirin tush kabi o‘tdi. In the sentence, we translate happy into Uzbek like shirin. While translating metaphor it must be paid attention to three aspects of metaphor, they are demonstrated below: a) the aspect of the degree of expressiveness; b) the aspect of the structure of polysemous senses; c) the aspect of the function of polysemous senses. We can look into the samples of the usage of metaphor in the Uzbek language: Endi “J” ga keldingizmi – dedi san’atkor jahli chiqib. (A. Kahhor). Niso buvi qizlari tufayli necha marta qo‘ydi-chiqdi bo‘lib goldi. (A. Kahhor).Usta Abdurahmon ko‘pdan beri Niso buviga: Mehrini Faxriddinga qilamiz, deb yurar edi.(A.Kahhor). On comparing above mentioned samples, it can be concluded that the meaning changes metaphorically in the process of translation the combination into the second language. Metonymy is characterized as figurative use based on association and considered as a rich source

of polysemous variation. As well as, in Uzbek there are also these kinds of features of polysemantic words and the words change its meaning according to the context with different words. Metonymical examples are given below in Uzbek are similar when we translate them into English: Ko'p og'izni boqishim kerak. - There are too many mouths to feed. Og'zingni to'latib gapirma.- Don't talk with your mouth full. Bu ajoyib yubka ekan. -That's a nice bit of skirt. Jonning o'z mashinasi bor. John has his own wheels. (G'ildiraklardan biri tushib ketdi.- One of the wheels fell off.) Jeyn "kattakon"ga turmushga chiqdi. Jane married a large bank account. (Jeynning bank hisob raqami bor. - Jane has a bank account.) On comparing the examples, it has become obvious that some sentences are translated metonymically into Uzbek, while some others are translated by using different words but not changing the meaning of the context, here are the examples of metonymical words in the Uzbek language: - Juvon xodimlar gaqaradi va so'radi: "Shu mahallalikmisizlar?" – Anavi mo'ylov kim? – Qalam orqasidan ro'zg'or tebratyapti. – Uning og'zini yopdi (jimqildi). We can see the metonymically translation into English in those sentences: - The woman looked at the staff and asked: "Are you in this neighborhood. Conclusion: Studies of the cognitive-semantic base of polysemy have shown that conceptual metaphor and conceptual metonymy, together with polysemy, represent the main mental processes that ensure the development of meaning and the generation of new meanings. On the other hand, while remaining the basis of polysemy, conceptual metonymy and metaphor receive the greatest opportunity for their appearance due to the anthropocentrism of communication itself and human experience. Accordingly, various transformations in the frame structure are inextricably linked with the reflection of the real picture of the world. Therefore, the regularity of conceptual polysemy contributes to the emergence of new meanings for words and is generated according to the same scheme, which makes it possible to predict the ways of further development of these meanings.

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